

**A GLOBAL HISTORY OF SOFT POWER: OUTLINE OF A
DIALECTICAL LOGIC FROM LIBERAL INTERNATIONALISM
TO NON-WESTERN SOFT POWER**

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Abstract

Building on the criticism that the positivist research agenda on soft power has failed to appreciate the plurality of soft power articulations globally and for its inherent Eurocentrism, which marginalizes non-Western perspectives, this paper proposes a hermeneutic historical approach to studying soft power, emphasizing the understanding of its diverse social constructions by different purposive actors in the international arena. Introducing the research method of global history into the soft power research agenda, this paper postulates the dialectical logics that informs the historical process of the globalization of the soft power idea, thereby revealing the relationships of dialectical opposition and mutual constitution entertained by the Western and non-Western articulations of soft power in international politics. This hermeneutic global historical approach to soft power overcomes Eurocentric normativity and technological determinism, thereby foregrounding the integration and appreciation of soft power from the Global South. Analytically, this approach discloses space for human agency and historical contingency in the historical study of soft power.

Keywords: Soft power, globalization, global history, hermeneutics, dialectic

Introduction

It is acknowledged that, with very few exceptions, the research agenda on soft power in International Relations (IR) revolves around either (1) purely theoretical elucidations on definitions, concepts, and methodologies for soft-power analysis, that is on such questions of how soft power should be defined and how it is expected to work, or (2) the study, comparative or otherwise, of single (national) soft-power cases

(Bakalov, 2019). To the first group belong those studies addressing such foundational research questions as: How is soft power conceptually defined in contrast to hard power? Is soft power to be measured based on, in Nye's terminology, soft power resources or soft power outcomes? Which are the most adequate metrics to measure soft power and its outcomes? What can be observed in the state-of-the-art scholarship on soft power is a general tendency toward consensus on the following, now well-established, points. First, soft power behaviors (agenda-setting, persuasion, and attraction) rather than the nature of the instruments (material or immaterial) utilized for their enactment do define soft power in contrast to hard power, and the two are distinguished based on a difference-in-degree rather than a difference-in-kind typology.

Second, the nature of soft power is not actor-centric but relational, thus the unit of soft power analysis must be the behavioral outcomes of soft power interactions, i.e., the behavioral (policy) change of a soft power target following a given soft power initiative on the part of a soft-power agent (Nye, 2011). From this follows that, third, because the level of analysis is the *relation* between the actors of soft power pairings rather than the actors themselves, process-tracing methods are more adequate for soft power causal analysis than are such static (no matter how longitudinal) measurements as opinion polls (Ohnesorge, 2020). No significant innovation has gained traction beyond these theoretical advancements.

Studies within the second cluster are mostly centered on cases: the soft power and public diplomacies of European countries, China, Russia, Japan, South Korea, Brazil, Iran, South Africa, and so on and so forth. As reviewed by Ivan Bakalov, the case-centered strand of soft-power research suffers from the same "indeterminacy in the usage of the concept" (what is soft power and what is hard power?) affecting the concept-driven counterpart, the neglect of the "dual nature of attraction" (mirroring the resource-versus-outcome problematique), and the obscuring of the hegemonic power structures wherein all soft-power relations are embedded.

Empirical studies on the outcomes or results of soft power can be grouped in the two categories of result-as-attitudes (measured by opinion polls) and results-as-behavior (measured by observed behavioral

changes), which parallels the concept-driven methodological controversy. Based on the review of the literature, Bakalov argues that empirical work proves to be the drive of theoretical innovation in soft-power research, especially by virtue of its consideration of concrete, context-specific socio-historical situation wherein each purported soft-power case is identified. That being the case, neither the concept-driven nor the case-driven literature has satisfactorily clarified the problem of causality. That is to say, the question of whether soft power matters at all in the causation of policy continuity and change in world affairs remains fundamentally unanswered.

This paper formulates a third, alternative approach to the study of soft power defined as a hermeneutic historical approach focusing on understanding the different social constructions of soft power produced by separate purposive actors interacting with each other in the international arena. As reviewed by Zeli (2024), the non-hermeneutic (that is, positivist) soft power research agenda faces the crucial challenge of appreciating and understanding the plurality of soft power articulations existing globally. In addition, the positivist agenda is also fundamentally wedded to Eurocentrism, in as much as it ignores or delegitimizes the non-Western articulations of soft power. The significance of developing a hermeneutic approach lies in the disclosure of analytical space for pluralism and human agency. This objective is fulfilled by outlining a global history of soft power through the historical process of soft power globalization, focusing on the dialectical relationships of mutual constitution of Western and non-Western soft power articulations.

A Hermeneutic Understanding of Soft Power

The attention Bakalov has brought onto the case-centered empirical contributions on soft power may well lead us to a more advantageous angle for approaching soft power in world affairs. While it remains true that, in the framework of Bakalov's review, the case-centered studies still remain wedded to a positivist understanding that the accumulation of data on soft power cases can possibly fuel further advancements linear in theoretical refinement and sophistication (assumedly, along a linear pattern of scientific knowledge accumulation and progress), the empirical engagement with the soft power *practices* enacted by

international actors inevitably confront the scholarship with those actors' *understandings* of what soft power is and how they expect it to work.

As already postulated by soft power and public diplomacy scholar Craig Hayden, soft power may be approached not necessarily just as a phenomenon objectively and unequivocally found in the empirical reality but also as a "field of practice", that is to say, through a "constructivist methodology of understanding soft power via its meaning in use", whose aim is "not to demonstrate soft power effects under specific circumstances, nor to rehabilitate soft power as a kind of normative theory" (Hayden, 2017).

Rather, the concept is presented as suited to a more pragmatic analysis, which illustrates the manner in which soft power is incorporated into strategic positions that actors take on to manage international environments through non-coercive practice" (Hayden, 2017: 334). This can be done, for instance, by the scholarly attempt to interpret the logics informing "how actors actively (re)define what soft power means through public diplomacy" (Hayden, 2017: 334) which stems from the underlying idea that "the practice of public diplomacy contains constitutive beliefs, encoded into practices like exchange programmes and explicit in policy recommendations and strategic discourse, about relations among states and publics, and how communication media are rendered *available* to states as levers of influence" (Hayden, 2017: 332-3).

Fundamentally, therefore, the matter is no longer to demonstrate whether and how do state actors produce tangible international political effects by means of soft power initiatives, but rather to uncover which worldviews and ideas of international politics and communication inform and drive such initiatives in the first place. This approach maintains that "[s]oft power's conceptual ambiguity is an invitation for the concept to be appropriated and resituated in localised discourses of international strategy" (Hayden, 2017: 349), which therefore lends itself to performative and interpretive analyses of the instantiation of soft power practices in their specific socio-cultural contexts.

Ultimately, this approach recognizes that "[s]oft power matters, not as a constant of international politics, but as a set of constitutive claims" (Hayden 2017: 351) on the state of the world and how state actors

should and are allowed to navigate it. This postulation is considered “suited for an increasingly necessary critical and pragmatic *diagnosis*, more than prediction and causal generalities, and they offer another way to test the limits and capacities of soft power as a framework for statecraft” (Hayden, 2017: 351).

Owing to the foundational role of the interpretative methodology, which is most notably incorporated and embraced by constructivism in IR, this diagnostic performative method of analysis discloses what we may term a hermeneutic approach to soft power. This approach contrasts with such positivist approaches assuming the existence of soft power as an objective fact that is manifest and observable constantly and invariably regardless of the different cultural and political contexts wherein it is practiced by purposive actors. While the latter approach alienates the element of contingency (e.g., geographical, social, cultural, political) from the analytical frame, the former approach regards contingency as the key to understanding soft power as a performative act constructed subjectively by actors embedded in complex social environments.

It is a plausible fact of reality that different actors conceive of soft power and the channels, means, and possible purposes soft power may be employed for, in different ways depending on the given actor’s perception, interpretation, and sense-making of itself and its surroundings. Since each actor is situated in concrete, unique, and irreplicable sets of environmental circumstances, no actor possibly sees the world and its position in it in a way identical to any other actor, so the way different actors understand the character, purpose, and uses of soft power inevitably varies from actor to actor, fundamentally depending on the specific contexts in which each actor is situated.

From a hermeneutic perspective, soft power is not what theory prescribes – but what actors understand of it and perform accordingly. The key is therefore not to evaluate, judge, and explain whether and to what extent the actors’ performances of soft power correspond to the theory’s prescription, but to interpret and strive to understand why they practice soft power in certain ways and with certain set goals.

To formalize, the difference between empiricist/positivist and hermeneutic approaches can be summarized as follows. Empiricism/positivism

emphasizes the objective observation and measurement of observable facts, seeking universal laws and generalizations through rigorous scientific methods. This approach prioritizes quantifiable data and strives for objectivity, often relying on statistical and/or experimental methods. In contrast, hermeneutics focuses on *understanding* the subjective meanings and contexts embedded in human experiences, acknowledging the influence of historical, cultural, and social factors. This approach emphasizes interpretation, context, and the unique qualities of individual cases rather than generalizable laws. The distinction lies in the emphasis on empirical observation and generalization in the positivist approach versus the interpretative and context-dependent nature of the hermeneutic perspective.

Historicist hermeneutics

Established that the hermeneutic approach stresses and focuses on contingency and the constitutive role of context, our understanding of soft power may further benefit if hermeneutics is applied not only to the spatial but also temporal axes. That means, we could not only focus on how different understandings of soft power vary across actors situated in different locations, but also how such understandings vary across time. This way, it would be possible for us not only to consider how, say, the United States and China understand and practice soft power in different ways and for different purposes, but also to contemplate these two separate state-actors change the ways they conceive of soft power and pursue it differently through time, that is, across different historical periods.

This approach combines intertemporal variation with interspatial variation and adds complexity to the identification and understanding of specific soft power cases in descriptive analysis. The vantage viewpoint resulting from combining the synchronic axis with the diachronic axis, besides adding complexity to the picture, benefits the analysis by shifting the focus further away from theory-driven universalistic definitions of soft power toward a more nuanced and context-sensitive appreciation of soft power as it is actually performed in the practices of relevant actors in the empirical reality.

This section has outlined and defined two possible perspectives from which to approach the analysis of soft power in world politics. The first one is a positive approach and perhaps the most intuitive and simple way to study soft power. We may term it as a positivist approach to soft power in as much as it theoretically assumes the objective existence of soft power as an independent fact of international politics and is merely concerned with its empirical demonstration, evaluation, and measurement of its supposed effects.

The second approach may be called hermeneutic and is based on the idea that exists only as the relevant social actors perform it according to their understanding of it. From this perspective, therefore, soft power is constituted by meaning underpinning practice. Hermeneutics, particularly in the historicist tradition, recognizes that interpreting phenomena requires an appreciation of their historical and cultural contexts. This means that understanding the meaning of soft power involves delving into the specific historical conditions and cultural frameworks in which it occurs. This historicist-hermeneutic approach rejects a timeless or ahistorical interpretation of soft power and instead emphasizes the importance of understanding it within the evolving and contingent context of human history.

In the next section, this historical interpretivist approach will be applied in an attempt to uncover the actual configuration of the practice of soft power in the current conditions of world politics, from a systemic perspective and in consideration of the historical record. The fundamental purpose of this endeavor is to determine the historically produced social constraints on the practice of soft power – defined broadly as the pursuit of international political influence by non-coercive (non-military, non-economic) means, hence as a category of practice historically instantiated. This understanding delivers the advantage of circumventing the several conceptual conundrums of the existing positivist approaches to soft power.

Toward a Global History of Soft Power

There is little doubt that soft power is an important, not to say a must-have, concept in IR scholarship. Individual scholars, including soft power's over-the-hill prophet Joseph Nye among others, have built on it their academic fortunes. Students, scholars, and the like all may find in

soft power an easy topic to write and publish on. In this age of the much-famed globalization and information and communication technologies (ICTs) when every material, hard fact of the world is unescapably attached with a representational, soft extension generated by media and political discourses, discussions and interpretations of the soft power role of this or that international phenomenon are always in demand. As a result, ink has been devoted to the captivating topic of soft power. Undergraduate, graduate, and doctoral dissertations mushroom in academic institutions all over the world. Now and then, papers on soft power pop up in more or less prestigious journals relevant to the IR discipline and sometimes cause bursts of great excitement in those scholars who find in the preservation of the soft power concept the means for their own academic survival.

However, it is necessary and important to point out, as it has been done carefully in the previous section, that the proliferation of conceptual and analytical material on soft power has not led to the desired effect of better clarifying the nature and operation of soft power in international politics. Rather than deploying efforts to theoretically conceptualize and theorize soft power, or to measuring and describe supposed soft power cases guided by such abstract conceptualization and theorizations, this article seeks a contextual understanding of the practice of soft power in the current configuration of global politics from a systemic perspective.

This requires circumventing the theory-driven prescription on the conceptual definition of soft power, so as to disclose to the condition for a performative analysis of soft power. In this perspective, we abandon the idea that there is an objective and universal definition of soft power, in favor of a more pragmatic approach that is exclusively interested in observing how different actors understand soft power differently and how they practice it in specific contexts. As timely discussed in the previous section, only a hermeneutic, non-positivist analytical attitude can effectively fulfil this end.

This section describes the examines the globalization of soft power – or, to be more precise, the idea of soft power – from a global historical perspective. As we already know, the concept of soft power coined in the late 1980s and elaborated through the subsequent decades by Joseph Nye refers to a country's ability to shape the preferences of others through appeal and attraction rather than coercion or force. Assumedly, soft

power has become an important aspect of world affairs, particularly in the context of globalization. While the concept was initially developed in the Western context, non-Western countries have also appropriated and reformulated it to suit their own contexts and interests.

The appropriation of soft power – or the claim to it – on the part of the non-Western countries is what we refer to as the globalization of soft power, a process that can be traced to the increasing interconnectedness and interdependence of nations in the late 20th and early 21st centuries. This article foregrounds the notion that the globalization of soft power witnesses a dialectical logic. According to this dialectical logic, the appropriation and re-articulation of the soft power concept by certain non-Western actors was a (dialectical) response to America's universalist claim to global influence through non-coercive means (soft power).

The only way to convincingly arrive at this finding is by adopting a hermeneutic-historicist approach to scrutinize the historical development of the idea of soft power – here defined broadly, as a category of practice, in terms of influence by non-coercive means – at the global level. Indeed, there is no way to conduct meaningful and consequential analysis of the contingent evolution and interplay of an idea across space and time if not by means of a global and non-positivist, non-prescriptive, and non-deterministic approach – that is to say, a purely descriptive global approach.

The historical analytical framework which best fulfils the double requirements of description and global outlook is, as this section argues, global history. As a recently emerging branch of historical studies, global history dismisses such idealistic, teleological-deterministic, linear, and ethnocentric interpretations of historical processes (typical of more the more traditional forms of historical investigation) and favors the appreciation of the global dimension of historical phenomena. Global historians are particularly fond of studying the transnational flows of people, ideas, goods, and technologies, the local-global entanglements of historical formations, their cross-border constitutive processes, their transformations, and global outcomes, and so on, all of which is fundamentally approached through a non-linear, non-hierarchical, and decentered conception of historical development.

What is global history?

Global history is an original research approach that has spread and become a topic of particular interest in recent decades in the field of historical studies. Described as “a form of historical analysis in which phenomena, events, and processes are placed in global contexts” (Conrad, 2016, p. 5) it is first and foremost an approach that focuses on connections and aspects through which the historical researcher relates different, apparently unrelated worlds, taking into consideration multiple dimensions of analysis. It would be simplistic to relegate global history to a mere perspective, since the contextualization of the topics addressed requires analysis of the degree and type of connections within networks shaped by transnational structures.

Common to global history and a number of apparently similar approaches (including world history, transnational history, and the histories of globalization) are numerous points of intersection: the overcoming of Eurocentrism and the national historical interpretative model (historical nationalism), the interpretation of distant connections through teleological narratives, the abandonment of internalistic explanations, among the most relevant.

Thusly outlined, global history is not much concerned with processes and dynamics within enclosed borders, but with what passes through them and the contextual transformation of issues and worldviews across time and space: “The significance of individual issues (say, for instance, slavery), changes fundamentally depending on whether we look at them from the perspective of Angola or Nigeria, Brazil or Cuba, France or England. Nor is the notion of what constitutes the relevant ‘world’ by any means the same across societies and nations” (Conrad 2016, p. 171), Particularly significant for contemporaries are the directions that have characterized global history since the 1990s, marking a turning point from the teleologically oriented historiographical research to the analysis of transnational connections; from comparative history to the study of macro-regions (e.g., the Indian Ocean, the Atlantic Ocean, Europe, East Asia); and from the history of civilization to polycentrism. All these have allowed the research to relativize the one-way perspectives of reading the past.

Global history discloses current global historical controversies whose thematization is intrinsically linked to the history of the present time and poses new challenges to the boundaries, values, and structures that have become part of the global legacy of the contemporary world. Clearly enough, the foremost controversy concerns the Eurocentric narrative that sees Europe as the only active figure compared to the rest of the world. In the search for the right balance between overcoming this vision and the risk of an unjustified marginalization of Europe, global historians position themselves on the ridge of distinction between (1) Eurocentrism as a dynamic of the historical process intelligible only through reference to the actual Western hegemony developed over the centuries, and (2) Eurocentrism as a perspective seeing Europe as the sovereign subject of all national histories reconstructed on the model of a universal and fixed development pattern typically reproduced in the conceptual toolkit of modern social sciences: “Europe acts, the rest of the world responds. Europe has ‘agency’; the rest of the world is passive. Europe makes history; the rest of the world has none until it is brought into contact with Europe. Europe is the center; the rest of the world is its periphery. Europeans alone are capable of initiating change or modernization; the rest of the world is not” (Marks, 2002: 8). It is precisely in the view of emancipating ourselves from this last Eurocentric master narrative that the new global historical approach is aimed at “provincializing” Europe and acknowledging the specificities and historical differences of non-Western societies.

The analytical problematization of the Eurocentric paradigm, analyzed as a process and as a perspective, is also of fundamental importance for the subsequent controversy, namely the one relating to the periodization of the history of globalization. This refers to a specific research area of global history concerned with those social relationships that transform into networks thanks to a certain degree of stability and convergence. Globalization is not defined as a meta-theory (of historical periodizations), and not even a simple object of observation; rather, it refers to a specific perspective that can help place the processes in broader contexts and overcome the methodological nationalism of the historical sciences.

That said, debates on questions of periodization can provide only broad indications, for a history of globalization should in any case not be a linear narrative of the growing connection of the world. Intense phases

of interaction alternate with phases of distancing and isolation, and this creates actual holes in the network that are not always mended. Ultimately, while the transnational exchange processes not only contribute to the homogenization of the world and the creation of uniformity with respect to Western norms (which is an important aspect of globalization as a perspective), they also unavoidably create constantly fragmentations, new differences and cultural specificities.

A decentered history of soft power

A global historical approach enables us to bypass some of the unresolvable problems afflicting soft power research (such as, first and foremost, the problem of causation discussed previously in this paper). History is by definition context-sensitive, and global history also captures the local-global entanglements that transcend and intertwine the specific cases under scrutiny. This is granted by the very nature of the global historical research agenda. As a field of historical study, global history focuses on understanding and analyzing historical events and processes from a global perspective. It looks beyond the national or regional narratives of traditional methods and explores the transnational, transregional, and global forces that have shaped human history. It examines the ways in which societies and civilizations have influenced one another through trade, migration, warfare, diplomacy, cultural diffusion, and technological advancements. This approach helps to uncover patterns, networks, and trends that may not be immediately apparent when studying history from a more limited perspective. It is no surprise that global history is gaining popularity and traction in History majors, especially if we consider its non-teleological, non-deterministic, and anti-Eurocentric commitments it shares with much critical, post-colonial, and feminist scholarships in the humanities and social sciences.

In practice, global history recognizes historical development as a complex interplay of various factors, including human agency, contingency, and unintended outcomes. Instead of searching for a predetermined teleological narrative, modern historical scholarship embraces a more nuanced understanding of history as a contingent, multifaceted, and multifactorial process. Contrary to the deterministic views of history, global history emphasizes the significance of human agency, individual choices, and collective actions in shaping historical developments. Global historians recognize the complex interplay

between structural factors and human agency, acknowledging that historical change often arises from the interplay of both. Finally, global historians strive to present a balanced portrayal of historical developments across different regions and civilizations by adopting the perspectives of agents situated in the Global South, while closely keeping an eye on their complex cross-civilizational mutual constitutions.

The decentered and interpretivist stance of global history invites global historians (and every trans-disciplinary scholar who draws inspiration from the global historical approach) to think in terms of globalization rather than diffusion; transformation rather than evolution; formation rather than building or construction; and to privilege the investigation of the dynamic mutual constitutions of the research objects over ontological essentialism (Conrad, 2016, pp. 79-89). Overall, global history pays attention to the local and the global, the particular and the overall; it reveals the complexities, interrelationships, and global dynamics that have shaped the present historical conjuncture; and it offers a more holistic view of historical processes from a truly *decentered* – that is to say, global – standpoint.

Applying a global historical approach to the study of soft power means to go beyond the particular ethnocentric perspectives, or methodological nationalism, in the study of soft power (for instance, the American erstwhile definition of soft power, or the Chinese version of soft power). By acknowledging such particularities, the global historical approach shifts the focus on the mutually transformative interrelations between them.

It is by so doing that the global historical approach emancipates the researcher from both the normativity that derives from the concept-driven abstract definitions of soft power and the particularity of case studies, as the latter are mostly oblivious of the definitional requirement necessary for relating each specific soft power case to another. Global history therefore paves the way for a decentered inquiry into the globalization of the soft power idea. Resting on these premises, it is hoped that the application of global history to the study of soft power may produce substantial contributions to the field's theoretical agenda.

A Global History of Soft Power

There is universal consensus on that, as a category of practice, or simply a policy catchphrase, enjoys today undeniable currency in the political discourse informing foreign policy of sovereign states. The case of the United States is itself a compelling case. Former U.S. Secretary of State Hillary Clinton's infamous advocacy of the smart power concept in 2009, during her tenure in the Obama administration the combination of hard and soft power articulated in Nye, 2011), is a rare and extraordinary case of a scholarly concept of academics being taken up by the rhetoric of top-level foreign- policy decision-makers with a big role in international politics – a kind of “trickle-up effect” of extraction of foreign policy (rhetoric) from theory. It is a testament of the coronation of Nye's smart power brainchild in the self-framing, and perhaps the very making, of US foreign policy.

Obama's epoch-making Pivot to Asia (started in 2011) figures prominently among the US policies and initiatives that were rhetorically justified in terms of soft power and wherein soft- and smart-power behaviors are involved. The Obama-Clinton conversion to the smart power creed (i.e., the belief in soft power's causal power in international politics) was thusly embodied in the incorporation of soft power in the US foreign-policy rhetoric. This case crosscuts multiple administrations, as is evidenced by the reiterated statements on the importance of what falls under the soft power umbrella in the US National Security Strategies of 2017 (Trump administration) and 2021 (Biden administration). But which was the actual historical trajectory of the concept from the global perspective of world affairs? And which is its current state compared to the past?

This section outlines the trajectory of a global historical interpretation of soft power. It starts from the liberal-internationalist phase and, throughout the process of its globalization, witnesses the locally situated national determinations of such an otherwise-abstract and purportedly universal concept. The relationship of mutual constitution of the Western and non-Western definitions and practices of soft power will be emphasized here. As will be argued, this relationship can be said to be characterized by a dialectical logic, motivated by its intrinsically oppositional nature. Overall, the Western and non-Western counterparts

define and therefore make one another, resulting in what can be interpreted as a process of inter-temporal co-formation of soft power across the local-global axis.

The liberal-internationalist moment of soft power

From a historical perspective, the US endorsement of soft power must be located within the formation of the US-led liberal international order after the Cold War, that is essentially characterized by: (1) the active promotion of democracy through economic, diplomatic, and military means (amounting to an application of the democratic peace theory); (2) emphasis on multilateralism (inspired by neoliberal institutionalism); (3) humanitarian intervention (and Responsibility to Protect); (4) economic globalization (capitalist peace theory); and (5) soft power diplomacy. Since the end of the Cold War, the liberal internationalist rhetoric provided the justification for the foreign policies of the United States and its allies, including the Gulf Wars, the Global War on Terror, and the numerous peacebuilding (humanitarian) interventions in various civil war theaters around the world. As the rhetoric of the rule-based (liberal) international order, liberal internationalism typically concealed the very particular Western international political interests under the cover of universal goals and values. On this basis, liberal internationalism can be said to be the ideological rhetoric of America's unipolar moment after the Cold War.

In international politics, soft power served to justify the continuation of the American predominance over the international system. At least two key aspects underlying the liberal-internationalist predicament of the American notion of soft power can be identified. First, Nye's soft-power gospel was positively welcomed by the Western policy and academic communities as a splendid opportunity for the rest of the world to be attracted and align its preferences and interests to the West, without the need for coercive means to be employed to that end. Western values, as well as the technological progress and economic achievements of liberal-democratic countries, were expected to be naturally attractive in the eyes of the peoples and countries in the rest of the world, which were in turn expected to be unproblematically drawn to change their own preferences to align with Eurocentric interests (Zielonka, 2006).

The soft power of American liberal democracy has long been considered normative due to such principles as of freedom, equality, and opportunity,

which supposedly resonate globally as universal ideals. Rooted in the values of individual rights, democratic governance, and the rule of law, American liberal democracy has historically been perceived as the gold standard for societal organization and governance. American cultural influence, bolstered by Hollywood, technology, and the spread of English as a global lingua franca, further reinforces its normative appeal.

Consequently, deviating from or rejecting American liberal democracy has often been viewed as an aberration, a departure from what is perceived as the natural inclination toward a system that champions individual liberties, fosters innovation, and promotes human dignity. Despite criticisms and challenges, the enduring allure of American liberal democracy persists, positioning it as a normative force in global affairs. We may call this the “Western liberal-democratic normativity” of soft power, which regards as natural (i.e., normative) to be charmed by and attracted to Western liberal democracy; conversely, it is an anomaly and aberration (i.e., it is heteronormative) not to be so.

Second, the soft power discourse is embedded in a broader *discourse of globalization* that emerged in the late twentieth century and gained significant currency in the 1990s. It encompasses the discussions and debates in academia, policy-making circles, and the media surrounding the increasing and much-talked-about interconnectedness and interdependence of economies, cultures, and societies worldwide.

A fundamental tenet of this globalization discourse is that the rapid growth of ICTs, particularly the internet and the social media-based Internet 2.0, played a crucial role in facilitating global connectivity and communication. As the old and trite adage of the globalization discourse goes, the internet and social media now allow virtually everyone to immediately access, generate, and share information worldwide, regardless of divides such as location, social class, level of education, and so on and so forth. Technological innovations are held to be the sole drivers of human progress along the linear trend of accelerating, irreversible, and pleonastic globalization of the global village. Consequently, in the framework of the globalization discourse, soft power is understood merely as a mechanistic outcome of the evolution of information technologies: the new ICTs now make the expansion of the Western soft power unstoppable, and there is little chance that actors located outside the West may possibly elude the charm of the ICT-

empowered soft power of the West. This “techno-informational determinism” rules out human agency, creativity, and historical contingency in the articulation and implementation of soft power in international politics.

The framing of technological advancements, particularly in ICTs, served the interests of the liberal international order. The development of ICTs, particularly the internet and social media, was framed in academia as serving the interests of the liberal international order and facilitating the spread of American soft power. Starting with Joseph Nye and all subsequent followers, scholars argued that ICTs had the potential to democratize access to information, promote global connectivity, and empower individuals worldwide, thereby advancing the goals of freedom, democracy, and human rights championed by the United States.

This framing positioned the US as a benevolent steward of technological progress and reinforced the idea that embracing American-led technological innovations was essential for participating in the modern world. In summary, the legitimization of US hegemony through soft power involved the strategic projection of American values, ideas, and policies as attractive, desirable, and even inevitable. This was achieved not only through the well-known cultural hegemony, promotion of democratic values, and ideational leadership, but also through framing of technological advancements as serving the interests of the liberal international order. Through these means, the United States sought to present itself as a benevolent hegemon whose leadership was not only beneficial but also morally and ideationally legitimate.

The legitimization of US hegemony through soft power involved the strategic projection of American values, ideas, and policies in a way that made them appear not only attractive but also desirable and even inevitable. This process was obviously multifaceted, encompassing diplomatic initiatives, cultural exports, economic relationships. At the level of the discourse on soft power, it was claimed that soft power is a liberal-democratic norm powered by informational-technological progress. These universal and eternal tenets were essentially upholding a linear and teleological idea of historical progress in the supposed age of globalization, believing that the evolution of human ideas and technology have determined a stage of history in which the time is ripe

for the liberal internationalist ideology to be spread globally without the need of coercion and be willfully embraced by all.

This view of history is fundamentally teleological, ethnocentric, and deterministic; and rules out the possibility that, through its historical trajectory, soft power could actually take different forms and meanings other than the one prescribed by normativity and teleology. Owing to such liabilities, this historical understanding of soft power and its role in the formation of the present historical conjuncture fails to account for the much wider actual trajectory of the soft power idea in the global world. This limitation thus motivates a different approach that incorporates and advances the most recent acquisitions in the historical analyses of soft power in view of a decentered, non-teleological, and non-deterministic perspective.

In contrast to normativity and determinism, a notable contribution in this direction to the literature on soft power is provided, among others, by Burcu Baykurt and Victoria Da Grazia in their co-edited book *Soft-Power Internationalism* (2021). The two scholars employ the term “soft-power internationalism” to conveniently capture the intrinsic connection between the original notion of soft power and the liberal internationalist agenda. They critically define soft-power internationalism as what became a “way to claim a benevolent form of hegemony” (Baykurt & Da Grazia, 2021: 5) and go as far as to conceive “soft power as a distinct historical period, from roughly 1990 to 2015” (Baykurt & Da Grazia 2021: 3).

By attaching this historicized clause to such an otherwise ahistorical, universal, and abstract idea, Baykurt and Da Grazia inadvertently yet valuably pay service to global history’s project of historicizing the supposedly ahistorical and provincializing what lays claim to universality. By systematically adopting the perspectives of some of the many non-Western countries – including Turkey, Brazil, and China – that, at some point in recent history, have taken up, appropriated, and re-articulated the concept of soft power to fit with their respective national conditions and contingent interests, especially in response to certain perceived changes in the global environment, the historicized treatment of the liberal internationalist moment of soft power paves the way for a

decentered and plural – that is global – understanding of the multiple local determinations of the soft power idea, their historical and geopolitical specificities, and the inter-relations of mutual-constitution (Hayden, 2012).

The Globalization and Dialectics of Soft Power

As is well known and told by scholars and pundits, soft power has become an important aspect of international relations, particularly in the context of globalization. While soft power was initially developed in the Western context, non-Western countries have also appropriated and reformulated the concept to suit their own interests and cultural milieus. The globalization of the idea of soft power can be traced to the increasing interconnectedness and interdependence of nations in the late 20th and early 21st centuries.

As globalization intensified, the ability to project and influence ideas, values, and culture became a key component of a nation's power. Western countries, particularly the United States, had been successful in leveraging their soft power through cultural exports, such as films, music, and popular culture, to shape global perceptions and values. However, non-Western countries recognized the potential of soft power and started to actively appropriate and reformulate the concept to promote their own cultural, political, and economic interests. This process involved not merely the blending of elements of their traditional culture, history, and values with modern forms of expression and communication, but also – and most relevant for the purpose of this study – innovation in their foreign policy rhetoric as well as conceptual and theoretical creativity and brilliance.

Perhaps, the soft power case that has so far drawn the greatest attention of scholars and researchers all around the world is the case of China. The country has steadily pursued an ambitious campaign to enhance its soft power globally since the early 2000s by promoting cultural diplomacy (including the creation and expansion of the Confucius Institutes), boosting the international broadcasting infrastructure, and improving the public diplomacy apparatus (Kurlantzick, 2008; d'Hooghe, 2015).

India has strategically utilized its soft power to enhance its global influence with its rich cultural heritage to project a positive image globally (Thussu, 2013). The Indian government has established Indian

Cultural Centers and sponsored cultural events to promote Indian art, music, and dance forms. Japan and South Korea both have come up and experimented with heavily and deliberately investing in the pop culture industry (J-pop and K-pop, respectively) as soft power resource for the purpose of national image fostering and promotion (Lie, 2015).

Russia, which has been creatively innovating its Cold War propaganda heritage, blending it with the most advanced technical instruments of the time to project its image and foster support with significant results around the world (outside Europe and North America) (Velikaya & Simmons, 2020) is also a case deserving attentive inquiry.

Finally, especially worth of mention is the case of soft power resulting in perhaps the most visible geopolitical effects in the soft power era: the case of Qatar, whose Al-Jazeera, ever since its foundation in 1996, not only projects a favorable image of the Arab city-state worldwide but also affected the patterns of alliances in the Islamic world (Seib, 2008; Ulrichsen, 2014).

Whilst obviously being non-exhaustive, the above list suggests that, in appropriating and reformulating the concept of soft power, non-Western countries have tried – and, in some instance, managed – to convert their unique cultural assets (resources) into positive soft power outcomes in terms of influence of global perceptions and interest promotion. By blending traditional elements with modern forms of expression, international actors have created a distinct and appealing image that resonates with international audiences (Anholt, 2007). This process demonstrates how the concept of soft power has evolved and spread across major powers, transcending its Western origins, and thereby has become a truly globalized phenomenon.

That said, what is relevant of most, if not all, of these cases is that they display how non-Western countries have utilized soft power strategies to *counterbalance* the Western influence and assert their own cultural, political, and economic narratives on the global stage. It reflects not only the growing diversity of soft power sources and the desire to shape global perceptions beyond Western-centric frameworks, but also the fact that non-Western countries seek to assert their own cultural, political, and economic influence in response to the perceived Western cultural hegemony and dominance in global affairs. This reaction is often aimed at challenging and pluralizing the narratives, values, and norms

propagated by Western powers. By so doing, they fundamentally challenge the soft-power internationalism of the West. The claim to universality on the part of one particular group of actors in the international system has been challenged by the affirmation of particularity on the part of a constellation of other particular actors belonging to the same system. All this resulted in the pluralization and globalization of soft power. Below is a host of examples.

The establishment of the Confucius Institutes around the world by the Chinese government can be viewed as a response to the influence of Western cultural and educational institutions like British Council and Goethe-Institut. In this perspective, Confucius Institute aims to promote the Mandarin language, culture, and values, projecting China's soft power and counter Western cultural dominance.

India's Bollywood film industry offers alternative narratives and cultural expressions that resonate with global audiences; its films often happen to emphasize Indian values, traditions, and social issues, providing a non-Western perspective on storytelling and entertainment.

The K-pop entertainment industry (including music, television, and films) has achieved significant international popularity, particularly in Asia and sometimes the West; it also powerfully disrupted the aesthetic standards of beauty among the youths in East and Southeast Asia and beyond (Kuwahara, 2016; Park, 2020); and it promotes a non-orientalist representation of Asian culture and aesthetics beyond the Asian geo-cultural milieu.

The reinvigoration of Russian soft power since the early 2000s under the leadership of Vladimir Putin may well be seen as Russia's attempt to recover and reassert Russian cultural, political, and economic clout on the global stage following the perceived decline of Russia's influence in the aftermath of the Cold War (van Herpen, 2016).

Qatar's Al Jazeera global network has positioned itself as a counterbalance to Western-dominated global media outlets by broadcasting alternative perspectives on global news and events, providing a platform for voices and narratives from the Arab world and beyond, and challenging the dominance of Western news organizations (Figenschou, 2014). Arguably, besides pluralizing the global information ecology, Al Jazeera has also triggered a chain of ulterior soft power dynamics in the Muslim world (see the United Arab Emirates' launch of Al Arabiya in 2003).

Conclusion

A global history of the globalization of soft power reveals a dialectical logic underlying all these cases of pluralizing soft power. The non-Western appropriations and re-articulations of soft power implied the constitution of such a non-Western soft power that is logically oppositional vis-à-vis the liberal-internationalist brand of Western soft power. While it is true that we must be careful not to generalize and essentialize categories such as “Western” and “non-Western” soft power, it must be recognized also that these very categories are consciously and explicitly performed by the very actors who identify with them.

When Joseph Nye or Hillary Clinton construct and celebrate American soft power and its purported universal appeal as an asset of Western liberal-democratic order, they themselves make such categories of the “liberal-democratic West” and the “Western soft power” something real and tangible. Likewise, the production of indigenous conceptions of soft power on the part of China, Russia, India, etc., which are candidly justified in the name of pluralizing soft power and promoting “non-Western” views on world affairs, allows us to keep the notion of “non-Western soft power” as a viable analytical category. Fundamentally, the dialectical opposition between soft power in the non-West and in the West carries a constitutive significance. The non-Western pluralizing claim to soft power makes itself out of the universalist (liberal internationalist) Western original claim.

Viewed from a non-causal global historical perspective, the decentering and globalization of soft power grows out of the very ethnocentricity and particularity of the very liberal internationalist moment against which it justifies and makes itself. This remarkable dialectic disproves the great soft power convergence predicted and prescribed by the techno-informational determinism and Western liberal-democratic normativity of soft-power internationalism. On the contrary, it magnificently recognizes and carves out analytical space for human agency and creative responsiveness to global changes to be factored in the formation of soft power in a global sense.

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A Global History of Soft Power – Zeli

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